

FORMATION OF COPULATIVE COMPOUND WORDS IN PASHTO AND CRITERIA FOR THEIR IDENTIFICATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7699425>

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Abstract: Currently, the differentiation of copulative units, the establishment of clear criteria for their differentiation is one of the topical issues of Afghan linguistics. The units that have a copulative connection in the Pashto language have not yet been studied as a separate object of research and have not become the subject of special analysis, having been divided into such groups as a copulative compound word, a copulative phraseological unit and a free copulative phrase. The analysis of the works of Afghan linguists also shows that in the Pashto language copulative units do not differ from each other, clear criteria for the allocation of copulative units have not been developed. In order to determine the classification of copulative compound words in the Pashto language, their structural and semantic analysis was carried out in the study. Copulative compound words were also analyzed based on phonetic, morphological and semantic criteria..

Keywords: copulative compound words, morpheme, interfix, copulative compound words in imperative form, phonetic, morphological, semantic integrity, stress, internal flexion, somatisms..

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Received: 03-03-2023

Accepted: 04-03-2023

Published: 22-03-2023

The combination of two lexical morphemes with an interfix under the noun+interfix+noun model is called "copulatives", "copulative compound words"²².

In copulative compound words in Pashto, its parts are semantically equal: none of them subordinates, defines or complements the other. From the morphological point of view, the second is the main part, because the root of the compound word is determined by it, which means that the whole grammatical form of the word is related to it. The parts of copulative compound words are either directly joined with each other, or they are joined with the help of the connecting element و (u, ā)²³: مور و پلار [moroplār] "parents", سوالوځواب [savāl-u-dzavāb] "conversation", توروږور [tōr-u-bōr] "essence of the work", شا و خوا [šā-u-xwā] "all around", ابو هوا [ob-u-havā] "climate", ميز و چوکی [mez-o-čawki] "furniture", کور و اور [kor-u-or] "property", لاس و پښې [las-o-pšē] "body". In this place, it is characteristic that the connecting element و (u, ā)²⁴ between two components acts as an interfix if it is used in a compound word, and as a connecting link if it is used with word combinations²⁵. For this reason, in the following places, we found it

²² Талыбова С.Э. Копулятивные словосочетания в персидском языке. – М., 2002. С. 32.

²³ Калинина З. М. Очерки лексикологии современного пушту. – Москва., 1972. – С.78.

²⁴ According to Z.M. Kalinina, the origin of the connecting element و (u, ā) belongs to the Iranian languages and was borrowed from the Persian-Kabul language. P-67.

²⁵ Талыбова С.Э. Копулятивные словосочетания в персидском языке. – М., 2002. С. 12.

appropriate to use the term "interfix" to connect the components of copulative compound words.

If the words are made from the exact repetition of two parts, then the parts are joined with the vowel ا (ā)²⁶: رنگارنگ [rangārāng] "colorful", مخامخ [məxāməx] "opposite", قسماقسام [qəsmāqəsm] "various". The repetition of nouns forms adjectives and sometimes adverbs. In the reduplication section of M.Ziyor's book on Pashto grammar, there are examples of combining repeated word groups with the interfix " ā " برابر، سراسر، مخامخ، کورا کور، لورا لور: ²⁷(الف منخي) " ā "

S. Rishtin emphasizes that the repetition of words not only connects with the vowel ا (ā), but also with the conjunctions "را، نا، په، تر" and serves for one meaning²⁸. In the work of both Afghan linguists, these models are studied in the section of "reduplication". In fact, the connecting vowel ا (ā) and the prepositions "را، نا، په، تر" are used as an interfix when connecting components, which is typical only for repetition of words in Pashto.

The "noun + noun" model of copulative compound words is very common, and in this case, the noun can be singular or plural, and the interfix و (u, ā) connecting the two components may or may not be present²⁹: کور و اور [kor-u-or] "property", غاري-غرونه [ghāre ghruna] "the whole area", مرگ-ژوند [marg jwand] "fate". The components of copulative compound words which come without interphixes, are equal to zero connection. In the "noun + noun" model, which is equal to zero connection in the plural, the morphological integrity is determined by the second part, while the first part also takes the form of the plural.

The least common form of copulative compound words in Pashto is the "adjective + adjective" model³⁰, which can be used to form both nouns and adjectives³¹: توروبور [tōr-u-bōr] "essence of the work", شنه زرغونه [šna zarguna] "rainbow", لوره خوره [lwara-dzəwara] "high and low". It is known from the given examples that both components of copulative compound words belong to the same part of speech.

Also, in Pashto, there are copulative compound words that have formed as a separate lexical unit, which are actually made-up words formed from verbs. As a result of using these words in the form of an independent lexical unit, they expressed a different meaning. Most of them have the imperative form in the second person singular. These derivations are copulative compound words in the imperative form, the components of which have a semantically equal relationship,

²⁶ Калинина З. М. Очерки лексикологии современного пушту. –Москва., 1972. – С.67.

²⁷ مجاور احمد زيار. پښتو پښويه. اکسفرډ، ۲۰۰۵. ص-۲۴۳.

²⁸ ص. رشتين. د پښتو اشتقاقونه او ترکيبونه. کابل، ۲۰۰۴. ص-۱۶۱.

²⁹ Грюнберг А.Л.Очерк грамматики афганского языка (пашто). –Ленинград, 1987. –С. 54-55.

³⁰ Калинина З. М. Очерки лексикологии современного пушту. –Москва, 1972. –С.78.

³¹ Р.Р. Сикоев, Именное словообразование в современном литературном языке пушту, Автореферат диссертации, М., 1967. –С.19.

and the components are formed by connection without an interfix (i.e. zero connection): راکړه ورکړه [rākəra warkəra] "commerce", لیدنه کتنه [lidəna katəna] "meeting", ناسته ولاړه [nasta walāra] "communication, meeting".

In the above-mentioned models, the order of the components is fixed, that is, changing their order damages the semantic integrity, and as a result, the words will return to their original meaning separately. For example: in the case of کور و اور [kor-u-or], both components together mean "property", with the order of the components changing (i.e. اور و کور [or-u-kor] "fire and house") the words individually give their original meaning and confusion arises in the translation. In this place, the interfix و (*u, ā*) between two components is also translated as "and" with the exchange of the order of components. Because "او" and "و" are synonyms³². Phonetically, "و" is weak when it comes between two components and sounds like و (*u, ā*). The difference is that "و" has a syntactic connection and "و" is a lexical connection. According to S.E. Talibova, the interfix -o- that comes between two lexical morphemes is never pronounced as -va-, -vo-, and if it is pronounced in the form of -va-, -vo-, such combination is not a copulative compound word, rather, it indicates that it is a copulative phraseological unit or a free copulative word combination³³.

From the point of view of morphological integrity, in copulative compound words, the second is the main part, because the gender, number of the compound word is determined by the second part, which means that all the grammatical form of the word related to the second part³⁴.

نن یی کاروبار ښه و، تر اوسه لا مازدیگرته ښایسته وخت پاتې و او ده، دا و ښه ډېر سگرت پلورلي وو.³⁵

[nən ye kār-u-bār šə wu, tər oša lā māzdigar ta šāyəsta wakht pāte wu aw də, da wu šə ɖer sigarət plorili wuu]

"His business was good today, there is a little time between now and lunch, a lot of cigarettes were sold".

In this example, the words کار [kār] "work", بار [bār] "load/burden" were combined to form the meaning of "business" using the interfix و [u]. Since the second component بار [bār] "load/burden" is in the singular, the following adjective and the past tense form of the imperfect verb ول [wəl] are adapted to it (ښه و).

In copulative compound words, phonetic integrity is characterized by the absence of a pause between the components, the fall of one head accent on the last syllable, or the presence of a secondary accent on the second syllable, while the main accent on the first. In Pashto, stress is free, not tied to a particular syllable of a word, as in some languages. When words undergo internal inflection or receive

³² مجاور احمد زیار. پښتو پښویه. اکسفرډ، ۲۰۰۵. ص-۲۰۲.

³³ Талыбова С.Э. Копулятивные словосочетания в персидском языке. – М., 2002. С. 41.

³⁴ Р.Р. Сикоев, Именное словообразование в современном литературном языке пушту, Автореферат диссертации, М., 1967. –С.12.

³⁵ اکبر بری. د سپورمی سرنگه، کابل، ۲۰۰۴م کال. ص-۴.

adverbs, the stress can move to another syllable³⁶. In the following examples, it can be observed that the stress falls on the last syllable of the second morpheme:

conversation	sawāl-u-ǰawāb	سوالوځواب
all around	šā-u-xwā	شا و خوا
climate	ob-u-havā	ابوهوا
furniture	mez-u-ĉawki	میز و چوکی
business	kār-u-bār	کار و بار
body	las-u-pše	لاس و پښې
property	kor-u-or	کور و اور
life/lifestyle	ǰwand-u-ǰwāk	ژوند و ژواک

In these examples, the interfix “و” is pronounced as -u-, added to the first component that precedes it.

On derivatives made without interfix, however, there was an accent fall of the first and second degrees. In this, the main emphasis fell on the second part:

literacy	lik lwast	لیک لوست
fate	marg ǰwand	مرگ ژوند
children	zoy lur	زوی لور
relatives	xor lur	خور لور
household items	kali kawdi	کالی کاودی
cattle	ǰwa xuskay	غوا خوسکی

According to N.N. Nuriddinov, the examples of such models are made on the basis of a certain template, have a specific accent system, and such units are whole and holistic. The interfix “و” can often be dropped. In the following examples, copulative compound words with the same content appear with the interfix “و” (u) and the phenomenon of dropping this interfix was also observed:

کور-اور (the words کور [kor] “house”, اور [or] “fire” combined to form the meaning of “property” regardless of whether or not there is an interfix و [u]);

تور و سپین — تور-سپین (the meaning of “mystery, unknown, hidden” comes from the words تور [tor] “black”, سپین [spin] “white”);

مرگ و ژوند — مرگ-ژوند (the meaning of “destiny” is derived from the words مرگ [marg] “dead”, ژوند [ǰwand] “alive”);

شین و زرغون — شنه زرغونه (the meaning of “rainbow” comes from the words شنه [šna] “blue” and زرغونه [zarǰuna] “green”).

³⁶ R. Inomxojayev. Pashtu tili grammatikasi. Monografiya. –T, 2020. 31-b.

Dropping of the interfix “و” connecting the components of a copulative unit is one of the criteria confirming that this unit is a copulative compound word. Because the absence of a connector between the components indicates that they are neither syntactic nor phraseological combination³⁷.

Orthography is not always a reliable criterion because there are no fixed rules for writing copulative compound words together or separately. In addition, Pashto still does not have clearly established norms of orthography³⁸. However, the collected examples show that copulative compound words in Pashto can be written together, separately or through a hyphen (لږو ډېر، کورټ و سکوت، نن سبا، وړاندې و وروسته،) (خور-لور، بنوونه-روزنه).

It was observed that the order of components in copulative compound words is usually based on such cases:

1. A less syllabic, short component comes first: شنه زرغونه [šna zargūna] “rainbow” (literal word: blue-green), ابو هوا [ob-u-havā] “climate”;

2. If the number of syllables is the same, the component starting with a vowel comes first (easy to pronounce): آلو بالو [ālu-bālu] “plum”, ارو مرو [aro maro] “willingly or unwillingly”. A component beginning with a consonant sound before a component beginning with a vowel sound is rarely found: کور و اور [kor-u-or] “all property”;

3. If both components begin with a consonant, the one that begins with a spirant or resonant explosive sound comes first: سوالو خواب [sawāl-u-ǰawāb] “conversation”, دلته هلته [dalta halta] “here-there”, مرگ ژوند [marg jwand] “destiny”.

This arrangement of components is related to the rhythmic-intonational structure of compound words of this type. Basically, such components are associated with rhyming harmony, which makes it easier to remember copulative compound words, ensures the stability, strict order of the components in them, and is closely connected with the general meaning. Rhyme gives the final form of copulative compound words, making it stable and at the same time easier to remember.

In the Pashto language also observed the state in which somatisms combine to form copulative compound words: لاس و پښې [las-o-pše] “body” (literal word: لاس *las* ‘hand’ va پښې *pše* ‘foot’), سروسامان [sar-u-sāmān] “property” (literal word: سر *sar* ‘head’ va سامان *sāmān* ‘things’), سروکار [sar-u-kār] “connection” (literal word: سر *sar* ‘head’ va کار *kār* ‘work’). In the above examples (لاس و پښې [las-o-pše] “body”, سروسامان [sar-u-sāmān] “property”), the first part of the components is singular, and the second part is plural.

³⁷ Нуриддинов Н.Н. Форс тилида копулятив қўшма сўз ва эркин копулятив сўз бирикмаларининг дистинктив белгилари. Монография. – Т., 2020. Б. 63.

³⁸ Р.Р. Сикоев, Именное словообразование в современном литературном языке пушту, Автореферат диссертации, М., 1967. –С.13.

The fact that the semantic relationship between the components of copulative compound words is synonymic and antonymic in many languages, including Pashto. The synonyms are as follows: لیدنه کتنه [lidəna katəna] meeting, کږې وږې [kaḍe waḷe] crooked, زور زهیر [zor zahir] old, خواربېوزله [khar bəwazla] poor, توفه ټکاله [toḡa ṭəkāla] humor. The following are examples of copulative compound words related to antonyms: لوی واره [loy wārə] everybody (lit. large-small), ناسته ولاړه [nasta walāra] conversation, meeting, راکړه ورکړه [rākṛa warkṛa] trade, لري نژدې [lire nəḷde] far-near, کښته پورته [kṣəta porta] up-down, لږو ډېر [ləḷ-o-ḍer] more or less. In addition, among the collected examples, the following semantic aspects were also observed: 1) names of the same type of close objects (generally two words of the same semantic character): میز و چوکی [mez-u-chawki] furniture, لیک لوست [lik lwast] literacy, خور لور [khor lur] "relatives, clan", غوا خوسکی [ghwā khuskay] "cattle". In the examples of this noun + noun model, it was noted that hyponymy and hyperonymy relations, which express a specific essence in relation to a general concept, as well as generalize the relations of species and gender, are extensive; 2) nouns of whole and part, general and concrete part: وقت و زمان [waqt-o-zamān] time-hour, ساعت و دقیقه [sāat-o-daḡiqa] hour-minute.

A study and analysis of copulative compound words in Pashto led to the following conclusions:

- in copulative compound words, its parts are semantically equal;
- from the morphological point of view, the second part is the main part, because the root of the compound word is determined by that part, all the grammatical form of the word is related to the second part;
- parts of copulative compound words are either directly joined with each other, or connected using the interfix و (*u, ā*);
- it was observed that both components of copulative compound words belong to the same part of speech;
- the components of copulative compound words in the imperative form have a semantically equal relationship, and the components are formed from a combination without an interfix (that is, from a zero connection);
- in the models, the order of components is strictly fixed, that is, changing their order damages the semantic integrity. Changing the order also changes the meaning. In this place, the interfix و (*u, ā*) between two components is also translated as "and" with the exchange of the order of components. Because "و" and "و" are synonyms. Phonetically, "و" is weak when it comes between two components and sounds like "و" (*u, ā*). The difference is that "و" has a syntactic connection and "و" is a lexical connection. The interfix "و" between two lexical morphemes is never pronounced -wa-, -wo-;

- in copulative compound words, phonetic integrity, absence of a pause between components, a main stress falling on the last syllable, or the main stress in the second part and the secondary stress in the first (mainly in derivatives without interfixes) is characterized;

- orthography was not always considered a reliable criterion due to the lack of strict rules for writing copulative compound words together or separately. From the collected examples, it was observed that they can be written together, separately or with a hyphen;

- it was observed that the arrangement of components in copulative compound words is usually based on the following conditions: 1) the component with few syllables and short content comes first; 2) if the number of syllables is the same, the component starting with a vowel comes first. It is rare for a component starting with a consonant to come before a component starting with a vowel. 3) If both components start with a consonant sound, the one that starts with a spirant or resonant explosive sound comes first;

- in the Pashto language, somatisms were combined to form copulative compound words. It was also proved with examples that the first part of the components is singular, and the second part is plural;

- the semantic relationship between the components of copulative compound words is synonymic and antonymic;

- in addition, the following semantic aspects were also observed among the collected examples: 1) names of the same kind of close objects (generally, two words of the same semantic character). It was noted that hyponymy and hyperonymy relations, which express the specific essence in relation to the general concept, as well as generalize the relations of species and gender, are comprehensive; 2) expressing the names of whole and part, general and concrete part is typical of copulative compound words.

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